

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Purpose and context statement template

Full resource

Table of contents

Introduction	2
Summary	2
Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework	2
Purpose and context statements	4
Purpose of assessment	4
The level of evaluation.....	4
Disciplinary context	4
Other contextual considerations	5
References	5

Introduction

Summary

This template supports defining and documenting the purpose and context of a research assessment (RA) process.

The idea is to consider the context of your assessment setting, specify and document the purpose and level of assessment, and take them into consideration when thinking about the different options for assessment methods and material. Think carefully who or what you are evaluating and why, and what is the level of assessment.

Before filling in the template familiarize yourself with e.g. the following SCOPE+i resources and familiarize yourself with goals of assessment presented by the European Commission (2019), <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/445286>.

- Indicators Guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>
- Guide on choosing an assessment method <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>

Template as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this template supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

[SCOPE Framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as check existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for stage C.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Purpose and context statements

Purpose of assessment

What is the purpose of assessment? Is it, for example, monitoring, learning or resource allocation?

The level of evaluation

What is the entity to be assessed? Individual researcher, research group, organization? What kind of organization is in question? E.g. multidisciplinary university vs focused, university of applied sciences, research institute etc. What is the size of an organization? Sum of researchers, teachers, research support staff?

Disciplinary context

Reflect e.g.: What kind of research outputs and activities are typical for the discipline? How do available database(s) cover research outputs and activities typical for the discipline? What is the orientation of research e.g. inter-sectoral, basic or applied research?

Other contextual considerations

Reflect country and geographical, national and cultural contexts e.g.: What are the typical research topics for a country based on geographical location e.g. arctic research or indigenous people? What is the national environment for research, for example, how is research funded, or how large is the research community? What is/are national language(s) and publication language(s)? Effects on publication language? Effects on the extent of the readership? Are there any issues within the country that have an impact on the country's research organizations e.g. war, a severe natural disaster, or a weak economic situation of the state?

References

International Network of Research Management Societies - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

